

Code Switching and Code Mixing In the Video Channel

Youtube “Korea Reomit”

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ABSTRACT: *The aim of this study is to describe the form of code switching, code mixing and the factors that cause code switching and code mixing. The data was taken from several Korean YouTube channel Reomit videos. Reomit's Korean YouTube channel is owned by Jang Hansol. He is a Korean citizen who can speak Indonesian, Korean, English, and Javanese. This research used qualitative descriptive method and the data collection uses a non-participatory conversational observation method. In data analysis, the researcher classified the data based on linguistic elements and described it using Hymes' theory. The result of this research is, the researcher found two types of code switching, namely internal code switching and external code switching. Then, the it found two types of code mixing, namely internal code mixing and external code mixing. The code switching that occurs is code switching from Indonesian to Korean, code switching from Indonesian to English, and code switching from Javanese to Indonesian. Furthermore, the code mixing that occurs is an element of English interpolation, an element of Korean interpolation, and an interpolation of Javanese. In addition, the factors that cause code switching and code mixing are to be prestigious, the speaker, the background of the speaker, the third person present, the listener, and the limitations of the code used.*

Keywords: *Sociolinguistic, code switching, code mixing, YouTube.*

I. INTRODUCTION

We are currently in the era of globalization, humans can live without limits. Lapasau&Arifin (2016, p. 47) reveal that Indonesia is a destination that has great potential and attractiveness for other countries. This global era has created free competition between countries. Indonesian is in demand by foreigners in this global era. Regarding this, Hardini, et al., (2019, p. 331) stated that currently many South Koreans come to Indonesia to study language and culture at various universities in Indonesia through the Indonesian Language for Foreign Speakers (BIPA) program. In addition, in South Korea there is also a university that provides Indonesian Language Department, namely Hankuk University of Foreign Studies (HUFS). Quoted from Info Campus News on May 14, 2020, the Indonesian Language Department is also available at several overseas universities such as the University of London in England, University of Washington in the United States and University of Melbourne in Australia. In addition to organizing language learning in universities in several countries, sophisticated technology also supports foreign students to learn Indonesian through the internet. The presence of the internet today makes everyone able to access anything without limits.

So far, a popular social media in Indonesia, namely YouTube. YouTube is a video sharing social media founded by 3 former PayPal employees, namely Chad Hurley, Steve Chen, and Jawed Kharim. The first YouTube video was uploaded on April 23, 2005 by co-founder Jawed Kharim at the San Diego Zoo (Corbuzier, 2018, p. 2). Indonesia's population who actively play social media reaches 150 million people. Of the many types of social media, YouTube is the most popular. In August 2017, YouTube entered the top three most frequently accessed sites in Indonesia. In the popularity of YouTube there is a term called YouTuber. A YouTuber is someone who

uploads, produces, or appears in videos on the YouTube website (Junawan&Laugu, 2020: 42).

Currently in Indonesia there are many successful YouTubers who have millions of subscribers. An interesting phenomenon from the popularity of YouTube in Indonesia is the emergence of Korean YouTubers who create video content using the Indonesian language. Korean YouTube channels that use Indonesian in their videos include *Jun Chef*, *Han Yoo Ra*, *Bandung Oppa*, *Sunnydahyein* and *Korea Reomit*. Many Korean youtubers, *Reomitis* the channel that has the most subscribers is owned by Jang Hansol.

Jang Hansol is a Korean man who was born in Daegu, South Korea on May 8, 1994. In his YouTube channel video entitled "At first I can speak Javanese" with a duration of 1 hour 10 minutes 48 seconds, he tells about his struggles learn Indonesian and Javanese while living in Indonesia. He first came to Indonesia in 1998 then he lived in Indonesia, precisely in Malang, East Java with his family. In Malang, he studied from kindergarten to high school at a local private school. He admitted that he was the only foreign citizen (WNA) who studied at a local private school at that time. After graduating from high school, he continued his undergraduate studies in Singapore. Hansol's experience while in Malang and his educational background about 26-year-old made him able to speak Korean, Indonesian, or Javanese fluently and can speak English with a Singaporean accent and communicates with his family using Korean language. However, when he was at school with his friends, he used Javanese and Indonesian, when he speaks on a YouTube video channel is very interesting to study with sociolinguistic approach. Saleh, et al., (2021) stated that Sociolinguistics is closely related to language contact events. The language contact that occurs in Jang Hansol's video with the other person tends to code-switch and code-mix. Code switching is a symptom of switching language use due to changing situations (Chaer&Agustina, 2010, p .107).

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Based on the problem, the researcher formulated two research objectives: 1) to describe the form of code switching and code mixing in the Reomit Korean YouTube channel video, and 2) to describe the factors causing code switching and code mixing in the Reomit Korean YouTube video channel.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Previous Studies

Many researches have been discussed about code switching and code mixing. The researcher found several studies related to this research.

Widianingsih, (2018) wrote about code switching entitled "*AlihKodedanCampurKodedalam Video Blogger: KajianSosiolinguistik*". This research is discussed about code-switching, code-mixing and the causes of code-switching and code-mixing. The results of this research found the forms of code switching and code mixing, there are 6 code switching data in the form of external code switching (outward) and entirely in the form of sentences, 13 code mixing data in the form of external code mixing (outside) and internal code mixing (outward). In addition, the causes of code switching were also found, that are the interlocutor, the speaker, changes in the situation due to the presence of a third person. The causes of code mixing are language limitations, informal situations, there is no proper expression in the language used and the speaker wants to show off his learning.

Ariesta, (2017) also wrote research on code switching term entitled "*Bentuk Campurkodedalam Video YouTube Kaesang Tahun 2017*" This research reveals the form of code mixing and the factors that cause code mixing. This research found that code mixing forms based on linguistic units, namely words, phrases, clauses and sentences. Code mixing is based on the language that occurs, it is aJavanese into Indonesian and English into Indonesian. In addition, it was also found that the factors

that caused code mixing were the background of the speaker, the interlocutor, the mode of conversation, the topic, for mere prestige, the use of more popular terms, the choice of shorter words, to refine speech, and the limitations of the use of codes.

Nugraha (2019) has also conducted research on code mixing, entitled "*Bentuk Campur Kode di Situs Berita: Review Berita Piala AFF 2016 pada Channel Tentang Game di Situs Detiksepakbola.com*". This study found six forms of code mixing, there are word element insertion, phrase element insertion, word repetition element insertion, baster form element insertion, idiom insertion (expression), and clause insertion. Based on the literature review above, it turns out that there has not been a single writer who has researched as the author proposes. This study uses the same theory as previous research, it is a sociolinguistic study that discusses code switching and code mixing. The object of the research is the Korean YouTube channel Reomit video. This research was conducted because no one has researched it as an object of research. Therefore, the researcher considers this study worthy of further research.

B. Sociolinguistics

Sociolinguistics is an interdisciplinary science between sociology and linguistics, two fields of empirical science that are very closely related. Sociolinguistics is commonly defined as a science that studies the characteristics and variations of language, as well as the relationship between linguists and the function of language variations in a language community, Kridalaksana in (Chaer & Agustina, 2010, p. 3). From the definition above, it can be concluded that sociolinguistics is a branch of linguistics that is interdisciplinary with sociology, by the object of research being the relationship between language and social factors in a speech community.

According to Lapasau & Arifin (2016, p. 5) the word "Sociolinguistics" is a new scientific term (neologism) which consists of the word "linguistics" (formed from the Latin word "lingua" which means tongue or language) and the prefix socio which means society and additional elements for the compound word –o which means something related and related to social society. Kridalaksana (in Lapasau and Arifin, 2016, p. 6) state that sociolinguistics is defined as a science that studies the characteristics and various variations of language, as well as the relationship between linguists and the characteristics and functions of that language in a speech community.

According to Wardhaugh (in Lapasau and Arifin, 2016, p. 6) sociolinguistics is concerned with research on the relationship between language and society with the aim of gaining a better understanding of the structure of language and the function of language in communication. Sociolinguistics is the study of the characteristics of language variation, the functions of language variations, and language users because these three elements always interact, change, and change each other in a speech community, J.A Fishman in (Chaer & Agustina, 2010, p. 3).

Hadi (2017, p. 1) reveals that sociolinguistics is the study of language related to social conditions (study of social sciences, especially sociology). Sociolinguistics as institutional linguistics (institutional linguistics), is related to the linkage of language with the people who use that language, Halliday in (Hadi, 2017, p. 2). Human behavior using language certainly has various aspects, such as numbers, attitudes, customs, and culture.

C. Language

Language is an arbitrary sound symbol system used by the community to work together, interact, and identify themselves, Kridalaksana in (Lapasau & Arifin, 2016, p.1). From this definition, it can be said that language must be systemic, in the form of symbols that we see and hear in symbols, and language is used by the community to communicate.

Nababan (1993, p. 1) states that language is one of the most distinctive characteristics of humans that distinguish them from other creatures. This language can be studied from various angles and pays special attention to the different elements of language and to the different relationships or structures. Language is a social institution as well as marriage, inheritance, and so on, De Saussure in (Nababan, 1993, p. 1).

According to Chaer & Agustina (2010, p.11) language is a system, it means that language is formed by a number of components that are patterned regularly and can be ruled out. Lyons in (Aslinda & Syafyahya, 2014, p. 1) said

that language must be systemic, in the form of symbols that we see and hear in symbols, and language is used by the community in communicating.

D. Bilingualism

The term bilingualism in Indonesian is also called bilingualism. Literally bilingualism is related to the use of two languages or two language codes. Bilingualism is defined as the use of two languages by a speaker in his interactions with other people in turn, Marckey and Fishman in (Chaer&Agustina, 2010, p. 84). According to Weinreich in (Aslinda&Syafyahya, 2014, p. 23), bilingualism is the habit of using two or more languages interchangeably. In addition, Bloomfield in (Chaer&Agustina, 2010, p. 85) state that bilingualism is the ability of a speaker to use two languages well. So, someone is called bilingual if he can use B1 and B2 with the same degree.

Bilingualism is related to the use of two or more languages in society (Bialystok, 2010). Although there are also terms multilingualism and plurilingualism, both of which refer to the use of more than two languages, the term bilingualism is often used to refer to the meaning of both, whether it involves two languages or is said to be bilingual or bilingual (Wijana&Setiawan, 2021, P. 257).

E. Switch Code

Code switching is the transition of usage from one language code to another, Wijana (2021, p. 37). For example, people switch from using Indonesian to Javanese, from Javanese karma to Javanese *ngokoor vice versa*, from the conversational variety to the official variety, from the official variety to the literary variety. In code switching, speakers consciously move from one code to another because they know the linguistic functions of each language code, for instance using Javanese for what, to whom, in what situation, and Indonesian for different situations or to talk about different things.

Code switching is one aspect of language dependence in a multilingual society, it means that in a multilingual society it is almost impossible for a speaker to use one language absolutely without the slightest use of another language or not (Suwito, 1983, p. 69; Andini, et al., 2022).

F. Mix Code

Wijana (2021, p. 38) states that code mixing is the use of two or more types of language codes in one utterance, but the transition function is unclear because speakers do not know for sure the different functions of each code. However, the problem is how to know that there is no particular reason behind the mixing because in speaking usually speakers have a specific purpose, such as respecting other people, joking, because there are other people or third parties, or just stylizing.

Code mixing is when people mix two or more languages or various languages in a speech act without anything in the language situation that requires mixing the languages (Tay, 1989). In Indonesia, this code-mixing often occurs in situations where people are talking mixed is Indonesian and regional languages. The salient feature of this code mixing is the relaxed or informal situation. In formal language situations, there is rarely code mixing (Mabule, 2015).

Code mixing occurs when a speaker of a language, for example Indonesian incorporates elements of his local language into Indonesian conversation. In other words, someone who speaks with the main Indonesian code has an autonomous function, while the regional language codes involved in the main code are fragments without any function or autonomy as a code (Aslinda&Syafyahya2014, p. 87).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The research has explained about the code switching and code mixing. Based on research on the Korea Reomit YouTube video channel, the researcher found symptoms of code switching and code mixing. The code switching found the data of code switching to the outside (external code switching) and code switching to the inside (internal code switching). Outward code switching that occurs is the transition from Indonesian to English, the transition from Korean to Indonesian and vice versa, while the inward code switching that occurs is the transition from Javanese to Indonesian and vice versa.

In the theory that has been presented previously, there are forms of code mixing such as code mixing for word element insertion, code mixing for phrase insertion, mixed code for inserting baster elements, code mixing for idiom or expression insertion, and clause insertion. In researching the video speech of the Korean YouTube channel Reomit, the author found a mix of code for insertion of word, phrase, baster, and clause elements. The code mixing found in this study is an element that comes from a foreign language, that are English and Korean and a regional language, namely Javanese which is inserted into Indonesian speech. The forms of code switching and code mixing that the authors are found as follows:

Based on the problem formulation that has been described in the previous chapter, there are several things that will be discussed in this discussion, 1) the form of code switching, and 2) code mixing and the factors causing code switching and code mixing. The following is a discussion of the results of research on several Korean Reomit YouTube channel videos.

a. Code-Switching Forms and Factors Causing Code-Switching

The form of code switching that occurs in the Korean YouTube channel Reomit video is code switching to the outside (external code switching) and code switching to the inside (internal code switching). The researcher explained the results of research regarding the form of code switching and the factors causing code switching in the Korea Reomit YouTube video channel.

1. External Code Switching

Conversation 1: (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)		
Place	:	Highway
Topics	:	Informal
Participants	:	01 Sunny, 02 Hansol
Atmosphere	:	Relax
01	:	<i>Saya juga ingin fokus dengan kehidupan personal pribadi, mengembangkan hidup saya.</i>
02	:	<i>Pokoknya kita duduk habis itu bakal ada hal menarik, ya pokoknya ke sana ya.</i>
01	:	See you
02	:	See you

The code-switching that occurred in conversation 1 was an external code-switching event, namely the code-switching from Indonesian to English. The code switching is marked by participant 01 "See you" and participant 02 answers "See you". Speech 01 was uttered by Sunny and utterance 02 was uttered by Hansol. Sunny is a Korean who can speak Indonesian, English, and Korean. So, it can be concluded that Sunny is also bilingual just like Hansol. He is also a YouTuber from Korea who often uploads videos in Indonesian on his YouTube channel, SunnydahyeIn.

The time when the story occurred when they had just returned from work as DJs for South Korea's KBS World Radio. So, it can be concluded that they were having free time at that time. The place where the speech took place was on the highway, when the two participants were on their way to the IFC Mall. The "see you" statement expressed by the participants was a goodbye greeting for the viewers of their YouTube channel videos, because they will start recording videos again after arriving at their destination, that is IFC Mall. The atmosphere of the speech was relaxed and seemed familiar because the two participants had been friends for a long time.

The code switching in the speech above is caused by the expression see you which is more popular than the expression in Indonesian "bye". So, participants switch codes due to the mere prestige factor. Indonesian young people also often use see you when they are going to separate. So, its use is indeed more popular and

prestigious.

Conversation 2: (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)		
Place	:	IFC Mall
Topics	:	Informal
Participants	:	01 Sunny, 02 Hansol
Atmosphere	:	Relax
01	:	<i>Iya desain uang. Aku lihat ini di Don Quijote Hotel langsung ngakak dong. Wah ini pas banget ini. Mas jutaan, harus toilet papernya pun jutawan juga.</i>
02	:	<i>Ga, tapi dalemnya kayaknya putih</i>
01	:	<i>Jangan putih deh, aku nangis darah nih..</i>
02	:	<i>Putih</i>
01	:	Are you serious?

Code switching in conversation 2 is code switching to the outside, namely code switching from Indonesian to English. The code switching in the data is indicated by the speech 01 "Are you serious?". Participant 01 is Sunny and 02 is Hansol. The place where the speech takes place is IFC Mall. The time for the regulation to occur is when the participants are having free time. The atmosphere of speech looks relaxed according to where they are talking in the cafe.

In the conversation above, participant 01 doesn't believe Hansol's statement that the toilet paper that Sunny gave him didn't have the money design as he imagined. Sunny was very surprised and suddenly switched the code from Indonesian to English by saying "Are you serious" to Hansol. The factor that causes code switching is the personality of the narrative. Sunny's background in mastering several languages such as English makes her switch codes without anything special. This was also followed by his interlocutor, Hansol, who mastered English. Therefore, their communication remains smooth. A very memorable informal atmosphere, affecting the above code switching event.

Conversation 3:(KR/SBPTI/10/10/2018)		
Place	:	Sunny's house
Topics	:	Informal
Participants	:	01 Sunny, 02 Hansol, Sunny's mom
Atmosphere	:	Relax
01	:	Padahal dulu aku bisa habiskan durian satu.
02	:	Oya?
01	:	<i>그지엄마? [Geujieomma?]</i>
02	:	<i>Ada iklannya. 옛날에두리안잘먹었요? [yenare durian jalmeogeosseo?]</i>
03	:	<i>어 [Eo].</i>
01	:	<i>혼자다먹었어요 [Honja ta meoggeosseo].</i>

The code-switching that occurred in conversation 3 was code-switching to the outside, namely code-switching from Indonesian to Korean. The conversation above takes place between participants 01, 02, and 03. Participant 01 is Sunny, 02 is Hansol, and 03 is Mama Sunny. The code switching above is indicated by the utterance 01 “그지 ? [Geujieomma?]” (Really Mom?), speech 02 “옛날에? [yenare durian jalmeogeosseo?]” (Did he used

to like eating durian?), speech 03 “*어* [*Eo*]” (Yes).

When the speech occurred, participants 01 and 02 were recording videos at participant 01's house for YouTube content whose topic was about telling experiences in Indonesia. When sharing their experiences they discussed about the durian fruit. Participant 01 revealed that he did not like durian, not long after that participant 03 appeared. Due to the presence of participant 03, participant 01 suddenly switched the code from Indonesian to Korean. The factor that causes this is the presence of a third person. Participant 03 is Mama Sunny who is Korean and her mother tongue is Korean. Therefore, participants 01 and 02 immediately switched codes from Indonesian to Korean to respect participant 03 and neutralize the speech situation. The atmosphere that occurred among the three participants above was relaxed.

Conversation 4:(KR/JBP-CMIS/08/02/2019)	
Place	: Siti Sarah's Restaurant in Itaewon, South Korea
Topics	: Informal
Participants	: 01 Hansol, 02 Hansol's Brother, 03 Waiter
Atmosphere	: Relax
01	: <i>일단, 메뉴가 좀 나시 고렝은 있고 소토 있고 그리고 굴라이 깜빙 있고 하고 싶은 거 있어 말해래. [Iltan, menyuga jom nasi goreng ittgo soto ittgo geurigo gulai kambing ittgo hagosipheun geo isseo maraerae].</i>
02	: <i>네, 다음은? [Ne, daeumeun?]</i>
01	: <i>미 고렝 있고 통생 있고 오포르 아얌 있고 렌당 있고, 음 오케, 내가 그러면 나시 고렝하고 소토 아얌 사 할까? [Mie goreng ittgo tongseng ittgo opor ayam ittgo rendang ittgo, emm oke, naega geureohmyeon nasi gorenghago soto ayam sa halkka?] 내가 통생을 먹을게, 그러면 나시 고렝, 소토 아얌하고 통생을 세 개 다 살게. [Naega thongsengeul mogeulke, geuryeomyeon nasi goreng, soto ayamhago tongsengeul se gae ta salke]. Pak, bungkus bisa pak ya?</i>
03	: Bisa
01	: Bisa? Mau pesen soto satu, nasi goreng satu, sama tongseng satu. Bungkus tiga ya pak.

The code switching contained in conversation 4 is code switching outside that it is from Korean to Indonesian. This code-switching takes place between two unrelated languages. The conversation above involves 3 participants. Participant 01 is Hansol, participant 02 is Brother Hansol, and participant 03 is restaurant employee. The code switching is shown in speech 01 “*내가, 나시, 통생을다* [*Naega thongsengeul mogeulke, geuryeomyeon fried rice, soto ayamhago tongsengeul se gae ta salke*]” (I want to eat *tongseng*, then I bought fried rice, chicken soup, and *tongseng*, so I bought three). After participant 01 called participant 02, the words "Sir, can you wrap it, sir?" (“*Pak, bungkus bisa pak ya?*”). The question was asked to participant 03 is a waiter of this restaurant. It can be concluded that participant 01 switched the code from Korean to Indonesian when communicating with the waiter.

The code switching that occurred was caused by participant 01 at first talking on the phone with participant 02. Because participants 01 and 02 were Korean, they spoke in Korean. The situation that occurs is in a relaxed manner, where participant 01 asks participant 02 what Indonesian food to buy. After determining the food they want to buy, participant 01 orders food to the waiter. Participant 01 suddenly switched the code from Korean to Indonesian when ordering food. The factor that causes the code switching is the interlocutor. Participant 01 changed the code because his opponent, participant 03, was an Indonesian. So, participant 01 wants to balance the language used by the interlocutor.

Conversation 5:(KR/PJPCUPKS1/09/08/2020)		
Place	:	A Hotel in Jeju Island
Topics	:	Informal
Participants	:	01 Hansol, 02 Jini
Atmosphere	:	Relax
01	:	Oke, jadi kita bakal ninggalkan tempat, terakhir.
02	:	고생했어요 [Gosaenghaesseoyo].
01	:	Chris 파이팅! [phaithing!]
02	:	파이팅! [phaithing!]
01	:	Chris!
02	:	성공해야돼요. [Seonggonghaeya dwaeyo]
01	:	성공해! [Seonggonghae!]

The code-switching that occurred in conversation 5 was code-switching to the outside, namely the transition from Indonesian to Korean. The conversation above involves two people, they are participant 01 is Hansol and participant 02 is Jini. Jini is a Korean who was helping Hansol decorates Chris' room for the proposal. The code switching that occurred was marked by the speech of participant 01 at first using Indonesian "Okay, so we will leave the place, last". Participant 01 expressed the above speech in a video intended for the audience of his YouTube channel, the majority of who are Indonesians. After that, participant 02 joined the conversation in the video by revealing "고생했어요 [Gosaenghaesseoyo]" (we've worked hard). Speech 02 explained that they had worked hard to decorate the room that was prepared for his friend's proposal. Because participant 02 spoke Korean, participant 01, who initially spoke Indonesian, then switched the code to Korean. This is clearly seen by his expression, "Chris ! [Phaithing!] (Chris spirit)". After that, participant 02 who said "성공해야 . [Seonggonghaeyadwaeyo]" (must be successful) and was answered by participant 01 "성공해! [Seonggonghae!]" (success).

The factor that caused participant 01 to switch codes was the speech opponent. Participant 01 compensates for the language skills of participant 02 who do not understand Indonesian. Therefore, participant 01 adjusts the speech used so that communication between them can run smoothly. The atmosphere in the conversation above is relaxed.

Conversation 6:(KR/PJPCUPKS1/09/08/2020)		
Place	:	A Hotel in Jeju Island
Topics	:	Informal
Participants	:	01 Hansol, 02 Jini
Atmosphere	:	Relax
01	:	Oke, kitaudah di mobil. 어떻게? 성공할것같네요.

		[Eotteoke? Seonggonghal geot gatneyo].
02	:	네. [Ne].
01	:	성공갈애. [Seonggong gathae].
02	:	성공해야합니다. [Seonggonghaeya hamnida]

Code switching that occurs in the data 6 is code switching to the outside. This is indicated by the utterance of participant 01 “Okay, we are already in the car? . [Eotteoke? Seonggonghalgeotgatneyo]” (how? Looks like it will work). At first participant 01 spoke Indonesian, then switched the code to Korean. This was caused by participant 01 speaking in a video intended for loyal viewers on his YouTube channel so he explained his situation being in the car to oversee Chris' surprise proposal to Sunny. After that, participant 01 switched the code from Indonesian to Korean when communicating with participant 02.

The factor that causes code switching is the interlocutor. In the conversation above, participant 01 speaks Indonesian while explaining the situation to the viewers of his YouTube channel. After that, participant 01 switched the code to Korean when talking to participant 02. This was because participant 02 did not understand Indonesian. So, participant 01 switched codes in order to communicate well. In addition, the background of the participants also led to the occurrence of code switching, namely participant 01 and participant 02 had the same mother tongue, namely Korean.

2. Internal Code Switching

Conversation 1:(KR/JBP-CMIS/08/02/2019)		
Place	:	Siti Sarah's Restaurant in Itaewon, South Korea
Topics	:	Informal
Participants	:	01 Hansol, 02 The Chef
Atmosphere	:	Relax
01	:	<i>Takonsitikboleh mas?</i>
02	:	<i>Oke</i>
01	:	<i>Loh, wong Medan opo wong mana pak? Orang mana pak?</i>
02	:	<i>Saya orang Medan mas.</i>
01	:	<i>Loh, kokisoJawapak.</i>
02	:	<i>Konco ne orang Jawa.</i>
01	:	<i>Kabeh?</i>
02	:	<i>Kabeh.</i>
01	:	<i>Oh konco ne wong Jowokabeh. Wes pirangsuwipak? Sudahberapa lama di Korea pak?</i>
02	:	<i>Tigatahun.</i>
01	:	<i>Tigatahun? Waduh.berarti di siniteruspak, kerjanya sebagai koki terus.</i>

Code switching that occurs in data 1 is inward code switching, code switching from Javanese to Indonesian. The conversation above involves participant 01, namely Hansol and participant 02, namely the chef. Participant 01 initially thought that participant 02 was Javanese. Participant 01 spoke in Javanese with participant 02. After the conversation, the fact was that participant 02 was from Medan. Participant 02 is also able to speak Javanese, but participant 01 changes the code from Javanese to Indonesian like this example “Oh *konco ne wongJowokabeh* (Oh, banyaktemannya orang Jawa). *Wes pirangsuwipak?* (How long have you been, sir?) How

long have you been in Korea, sir?"

The factor that causes code switching in the above speech is the speaker. Participant 01 tries to harmonize communication with participant 02. It is indicated by the participant repeating the speech that has the same meaning. Participant 01 did so because he considered his interlocutor who he did not know whether participant 02 understood the meaning of his speech or not. This is because participant 01 and participant 02 do not clearly know each other's language skills. The atmosphere at an Indonesian restaurant in Seoul is relaxed.

A. Code Mixing Forms and Causes of Code Mixing Outer Code Mixing

Based on research on the Korean YouTube channel Reomit video, the author found two foreign languages inserted in Indonesian speech in the video. In the analysis stage, the researcher has described the code-mixing data that the author found in the Reomit Korean YouTube channel video. The following is a discussion of the outer code mixing that the author has found.

1. Intangible Insertion of Words

Based on the theoretical study in the previous chapter, the word is the smallest unit in morphology that can form phrases, clauses, sentences, and discourses. In this research, it was found that outer code mixing contained the insertion of foreign language word elements in Indonesian speech. The outer code mixing is the insertion of English and Korean words. The following is an example of outer code mixing for the insertion of words in the Korean Reomit YouTube channel video. Sociolinguistic

01	<i>Jadi, ternyata kalo aku search di Naver maps, untuk Kota Seoul munculnya tiga, tapi di antarainya yang satu ini kayak kurang tepat ya.</i> (KR/JBP-CMIS/08/02/2019)
02	Saya minggu akhir ke 독서실 [deokseosil], jadi harusnya bawa buku-buku dan 도시락 [dosirak]. (KR/UDAKI-KNMNKG /28/12/2018)
03	Ini kalo di Korea ga pake 마보 [pabo]. (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)

In example (1), the insertion code of the English element is mixed. Speech (1) is a code mixing of the insertion of English verbs (verbs) in the use of Indonesian based on (Tahir et al., 2018). Hansol revealed this statement in a video entitled JBP-CMIS. Rahman, (2019. P. 72) state that the speech situation in the video is relaxed. At that time, Hansol was looking for an Indonesian restaurant in Seoul via the internet.

The factor that causes code mixing is that search words are more popular than their Indonesian equivalents. So, the vocabulary is rated higher in social value than the Indonesian equivalent. Another thing that causes code mixing is the speaker's educational background. As it explained in the previous chapter, he is a bachelor's degree graduate at the Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology (RMIT) University Singapore. So, it can be concluded that his English skills are very good. Therefore, the utterances often involve code mixing for the insertion of English elements.

In the speech example (2) there is the insertion of Korean noun elements (nouns). The statement above was expressed by *Jongdae* in the UDAKI-KMNKG video. In the video, *Hansol* and *Jongdae* are sharing their experiences about the differences between schools in Korea and Indonesia. They chatted in a park in Seoul, South Korea. *Jongdae's* speech has the insertion of a Korean noun (noun) element, namely [*dosirak*]. In Indonesian [*dosirak*] is a lunchbox or food box. The situation in the speech is relaxed because the relationship between the two speakers is good friends. *Jongdae* is a Korean man who can speak Indonesian because he majored in Indonesian at HUFHS Hankuk University of Foreign Studies, South Korea.

The factor that causes code mixing is that speakers have limited use of code. The speaker does not know the equivalent vocabulary in Indonesian so that his speech is code-mixed. Another factor that influences the occurrence of code mixing is the speech partner. This can be seen clearly because the interlocutor has the same regional background, namely both Koreans. So, it can be concluded that Hansol definitely

understands *Jongdae's* speech even though there is an insertion of Korean language elements in the speech. Therefore, communication between them will continue to run smoothly.

An example of speech (3) is the insertion of a Korean adjective. Sunny said this in the HDKS video. Sunny and Hansol in the video are exchanging gifts at one of the cafes at IFC Mall, South Korea. The atmosphere was very relaxed because they had been friends for a long time. Sunny has a similar background to Hansol, who is a Korean who has lived in Indonesia for a dozen years. Sunny also works as a YouTuber. Speech (3) is an outer code mixing because there is a Korean adjective (*pabo*). In Indonesian, (*pabo*) means stupid. At that time, Sunny gave a gift of a gel patch to Hansol. The gel patch serves to cool the feet in the summer.

The factor that causes code mixing is the cultural background of the speakers. Sunny wanted to explain that the gift she gave was very good, so good that if you were in Korea not using the gel patch would be stupid. Sunny conveys stupid vocabulary in Korean so that it sounds smoother when heard by loyal viewers of the Korean Reomit YouTube channel, which are mostly Indonesian. Another factor that causes code mixing is the speaking partner. As previously explained, Hansol and Sunny have the same regional background, which is from Korea. Communication between them continues to run smoothly because they are bilingual. Insertion of Phrase Formal Elements.

In accordance with the theoretical study that has been described in Chapter II, code mixing at the phrase level is lower than code mixing at the clause level. According to Kridalaksana (2008, p. 6) a phrase is a combination of two or more words that are not predicative in nature, the combination can be close, can be tenuous; such as high mountains. Based on the results of the study, the authors found outward code mixing (outer code mixing) the insertion of embodied elements of English and Korean phrases. The following is an example of inserting a phrase in the Korean YouTube channel Reomit's video.

01	<i>Oh, berarti kalo misalnya pas fine dust di Korea agak tinggi atau musim panas seger dong. (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)</i>
02	<i>Ini bagus banget, aku tahun lalu atau dua tahun lalu pake, ini kayak 여름 강추템 [yeoreum kangchuthem]. (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)</i>

Speech (1) is a code-mixed insertion of English noun phrases (noun). Hansol revealed this statement in the HDKS video. At that time, he was chatting with Sunny at a cafe located at IFC Mall, South Korea. The English element contained in the speech is "fine dust" in Indonesian which means debuhalus. The atmosphere is relaxed because the relationship between the two is good friends. In the story, Sunny was given a gift in the form of a cooling mask. Cooling mask is a mask that can provide a cooling sensation when worn.

The factor that causes speakers to mix code is Hansol's educational background, who graduated from S-1 in Singapore. Therefore, Hansol is accustomed to using English vocabulary in his speech. The second factor is the interlocutor. In the story above, Hansol's interlocutor is Sunny. Sunny is bilingual just like Hansol. So, it can be concluded that their conversation will run smoothly even though there is a code mixing of the insertion of English elements.

In speech (2), there is a code mixing for the insertion of Korean noun phrases. This can be seen clearly because of the emergence of the vocabulary [yeoreumkangchuthem]. In Indonesian [yeoreumkangchuthem] means summer recommendation item. [yeoreum] means summer, and [kangchuthem] means recommended item. The above statement was expressed by Sunny. The words were spoken casually, because Sunny's interlocutor was her best friend. They chat at a cafe located at IFC Mall, South Korea. During the conversation, Sunny was giving a gift of a gel patch to Hansol.

The factor that causes code mixing is that the speaker has an intention in the speech. Sunny tried to convince Hansol, that the gift he gave was a good thing. It was marked by Sunny calling the gift a summer recommendation item. Sunny did code mixing because they both spoke the same mother tongue, which was Korean. By using terms in Korean, the speakers hope that their interlocutors better understand the meaning of

their speech.

2. Baster Elemental Insertion

The researcher has described the previous discussion about the insertion of word and phrase elements. In this study, it also found baster elements that were inserted in the speech of the Korean Reomit YouTube channel video. Baster is a combination of two different language elements to form a meaning.

01	<i>Atau mereka sendiri belum memarketing nya melalui website-website Korea, itu yang disayangkan. (KR/JBP-CMIS/08/02/2019)</i>
02	<i>Saking excited-nya mau jelasin jadinya kan kebablasan gitu. (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)</i>

Speech (1) is a code-mixing speech in the form of a baster that Hansol revealed in the JBP-CMIS video. The code mixing is marked by the emergence of baster marketing. If interpreted in Indonesian, to market means to market. The code mixing that occurs is in the form of baster with clofixmekan (Indonesian) + word (English). So clofixes are affixed with the word market and the suffix -kan. In Indonesian, market means market. The word market if it is added with clofix, it becomes marketing.

The atmosphere that occurs in casual speech. Speech (1) contains a disappointment, which is indicated by the word unfortunate. The factor that causes code mixing is the background of the speaker. A bilingual speaker who does code-mixing does not have a specific purpose.

Example of speech (2) is mixing code baster English word pattern + Indonesian suffix. This is clearly seen, that the emergence of the word excited in Indonesian speech. Excited in Indonesian can be interpreted as interested. The word excited has the definition of being interested. Sunny meant to convey that she was so intrigued, she went too far when explaining the function of the gift she gave Hansol. At that time, Sunny gave many gifts to Hansol and immediately explained the function of each gift. The place of the story is a cafe at IFC Mall, South Korea. The atmosphere of the speech was relaxed and seemed familiar.

The factor that causes code mixing is the background of the speaker who is a bilingual. His interlocutor, Hansol, is also a bilingual who can speak English like himself. So, the speech that occurs tends to be code-mixing symptoms.

3. Insertion of Intangible Elements Clause

In the previous explanation, the researcher has explained the results of the code-mixing research in the form of clause elements. A clause is a syntactic unit which is above the phrase unit and below the sentence unit, in the form of a series of words with predicative construction. In this study, the authors found the insertion of English and Korean clauses. The following is an example of a clause insertion code mix that the author found in the Reomit Korean YouTube channel video.

01	<i>Jangan lupa untuk selalu support Hansol and always support him whatever he does. (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)</i>
02	<i>Jadi kita harus bisa nahan, ya, 이겨 진짜, 이겨 진짜 재미대! [igeo jinjja, igeo jinjja jaemidae]. (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)</i>

Speech (1) is code mixing for the insertion of English clauses in Indonesian speech. The code mixing that occurs is marked "Don't forget to always support Hansol and always support him whatever he does". In Indonesian it said "Janganlupauntukselalu support Hansol and always support him whatever he does". The speech appears in a video entitled HDKS. The atmosphere of the speech is relaxed and the place where the speech takes place at the IFC Mall cafe, South Korea. The sentence above was expressed by Sunny. Sunny tries to invite loyal viewers of the Korean channel Reomit to always support Hansol.

The factor that causes code mixing is the background of the speaker who is bilingual, so he mixes the code in his speech. Another thing that causes code mixing is the desire to be just prestigious, so that the expectation

sounds more classy. Because English is considered to have a higher social value. In addition, the interlocutor is also bilingual, so it is certain that the interlocutor understands the speech.

Example of speech (2) is code mixing of Korean clause insertion. This is evidenced by this utterance "So we have to be able to hold it, huh, , !" [*igeojinja, igeojinjjaemidae*]. In Indonesian, [*igeo*] means this, [*jinja*] means very, [*Jaemi*] means pleasant, [*dae*] means the word. The utterance means "He said this is very, very fun". Sunny said this in a video entitled HDKS. The atmosphere of the story above is relaxed and the place of speech is at the IFC Mall cafe, South Korea. At that time, Sunny gave a gift of saltpeter powder to play a game. The game requires refraining from burping.

The factor that causes code mixing is that the speaker intends to convince his interlocutor to believe that the gift he gives is very useful. Speakers do insert elements of the Korean language because of their similar cultural background. So, if the message is conveyed in Korean, the speech will express his opinion more.

4. Inner Code Mixing

In the previous explanation, the researcher explained that there are two types of code mixing on the Korean YouTube channel Reomit, namely outer code mixing and inner code mixing. The inner code mixing that the writer found is code mixing for the insertion of Javanese language elements in Indonesian speech. The following is a discussion about code mixing into (outer code mixing) the insertion of Javanese language elements in communication using Indonesian on the Reomit Korean YouTube video channel.

5. Word Elements Insertion

At this stage, the researcher discussed the form of code mixing insertion of Javanese language elements and the factors that cause code mixing to occur. The following is an example of inserting Javanese pronominals (pronouns) in Indonesian speech on the Reomit Korean YouTube channel video.

01	<i>Jadi mumpung sudah di sini, coba mau telepon kakakku, mungkin mau menu apa saja, tak pastikan. (KR/JBP-CMIS/08/02/2019)</i>
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An example of speech (1) is a mixed code utterance of inserting pronouns in Javanese, Indonesian speech. This is indicated by the word uncertain. The word "no" in Indonesian means "me". The above statement occurred in the Korean Reomit YouTube channel video entitled JBP-CMIS. In the video, Hansol intends to call his sister who wants to eat Indonesian food. The atmosphere of the speech is relaxed because it is not official. The place where the story takes place is Hansol's house.

The factor that causes code mixing is the background of the speaker. The speaker has lived in Malang, East Java for a dozen years. So, he has a habit of using Javanese. It can be concluded that the occurrence of code mixing is due to habitual factors and is supported by a relaxed atmosphere. The topic of conversation is informal. The speech is intended for the audience of the Korean Reomit YouTube channel, the majority of who are Indonesians. So, it can be concluded that if Hansol inserts Javanese pronouns in his speech, the audience will still understand the meaning he is conveying.

6. Penyisipan Unsur Berwujud Klausa

The researcher found the insertion of a Javanese clause in Indonesian speech on the Reomit Korean YouTube channel video. In the following, the author describes an example of inserting a Javanese clause in a video entitled KR/JBP-CIMS and HDKS.

01	<i>Ini bakal tak eman, tak sayang-sayang dulu, pas lagi uhuk uhuk baru tak pake. (KR/HDKS/07/06/2019)</i>
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In speech (1) there is the insertion of an element of the Javanese language, namely bukaneman. In Indonesian it doesn't mean me, eman means too bad. Hansol stated the above statement in a video entitled HDKS. At that

time, Hansol was given a gift by Sunny which was useful for helping breathing in winter and autumn. The atmosphere of Hansol's speech at the cafe seemed relaxed. The speaker was so happy to be given the gift that he said "Initidakaman". In Indonesian it means "iniakansangatsayang."

The factor that causes code mixing is the background of speakers who are already accustomed to speaking Javanese. So, speakers do code mixing because of habit and supported by a relaxed atmosphere. This is also related to the audience of his YouTube channel, which is mostly Indonesian. So, it can be concluded that most of the audience can understand Hansol's speech.

V. CONCLUSION

In this research the researcher examined several videos with the titles HDKS, JBP-CMIS, JBP-CMIS, UDAKI-KNMINKG, PJPCUPKS1, and SBPTI. Based on the the result that the researcher have described in the previous chapter, it found two types of code switching, namely internal code switching and external code switching. In addition, it also found two types of code mixing, namely inner code mixing and outer code mixing.

The code mixing that the researcher found consisted of inserting elements in the form of words, inserting elements in the form of phrases, inserting elements in the form of baster, and inserting elements in the form of clauses. The code mixing found was in the form of inserting English elements, inserting Korean language elements, and inserting Javanese language elements. Moreover, it did not find the insertion of elements of repetition of words and the insertion of expressions or idioms.

The factors that cause code switching in the research data that the researcher find are the desire to be just prestigious, the speaker and the speaker's personality, the background of the speaker, the presence of a third person, and the interlocutor. Furthermore, the factors that cause code mixing in the research data that the authors find are the use of more popular terms, the interlocutor, the background of the speaker, the speaker has a specific purpose, the desire to be prestigious, and the limitations of the use of the code.

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